

Supplementary Information for:

Schönauer, M., Prinz, R., Väättäinen, K., Astrup, R., Pszenny, D., Lindeman, H., et al. (2022). Spatio-temporal prediction of soil moisture using soil maps, topographic indices and SMAP retrievals. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 102730. doi: 10.1016/j.jag.2022.102730

Supplementary Table S2. Fifteen land model constants, available from Reichle, R., Lannoy, G. de, Koster, R., Crow, W., Kimball, J. & Liu, Q. (2020) *SMAP L4 Global 9 km EASE-Grid Surface and Root Zone Soil Moisture Land Model Constants, Version 5*. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5067/5C36BVQZW28K>, that were considered for modelling soil moisture content.

* indicates variables which were kept as input after checking for redundancy and co-variation.

Data field name	Unit	Description
*clsm_cder1	kg m ⁻²	Catchment deficit at which baseflow ceases
*clsm_cder2	kg m ⁻²	Maximum water holding capacity of land field
clsm_dzgt1	m	Thickness of soil heat diffusion model layer 1
clsm_dzgt2	m	Thickness of soil heat diffusion model layer 2
clsm_dzgt3	m	Thickness of soil heat diffusion model layer 3
clsm_dzgt4	m	Thickness of soil heat diffusion model layer 4
clsm_dzgt5	m	Thickness of soil heat diffusion model layer 5
clsm_dzgt6	m	Thickness of soil heat diffusion model layer 6
*clsm_dzpr	m	Thickness of profile soil moisture layer (“depth-to-bedrock” in the Catchment model)
clsm_dzrz	m	Thickness of root zone soil moisture layer
clsm_dzsf	m	Thickness of surface soil moisture layer
clsm_dztsurf	m	Thickness of soil layer associated with surface_temp
*clsm_poros	m ³ m ⁻³	Soil porosity
*clsm_veghgt	m	Vegetation canopy height
clsm_wp	m ³ m ⁻³	Soil wilting point